

A STUDY OF HEADLINES IN PRINT MEDIA

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Abstract:

The title of the printed matter is very much attractive, from the language-point of view. The folk-culture, with its proverbs, idioms and sayings has been sparingly and abundantly used in it. As the powerful, connotative language is used in the title, it is very easy to understand the central idea or theme of the news-story. So, the readers who do not have enough time to read the whole news-story; can grasp the matter within a few seconds simply from its title. The point of readability is important in such cases. The readability of a news-story depends much upon the use of language. The language used must be both sweet and useful. It should not be barren and mechanical and denotative. Neither should it be ambiguous, because it encourages incomplete understanding or misunderstanding of the readers. A reader without proper understanding of the matter, often baffles, misunderstands and then leads himself to the deterioration of the social values. For the fair understanding of the current social life the most essential thing is living life healthily without which there is no chance of enhancement of the socio-cultural values.

For that, the media men must use language properly avoiding the words that are related to the caste, creed and religion as such.

Keywords:

Headlines, title, language, news-story, print-medium

Introduction –

It is a world-wide-known-fact that Journalism is the fourth pillar or estate of democracy. The Journalist media are of three types: the first, web medium, the second, Electric Medium and the third, print medium.

Journalism has developed a lot in the 21st century. Nowadays, nobody is ignorant about the spectacular-strides taken by the modern technology. The whole world is busy getting access to either the website or the electronic media on the wider scale. Our modern world is developing and advancing with an exceptional speed. Nowadays our culture cuts itself into its many faces and all these faces are covered by the print media. The print media is revealing the social reality today.

We have an internet facility in our cellphones or mobiles. One does not need to go to the nearest internet cafe for browsing, because one's cellphone is providing all such facilities at home. Again the electronic medium is still competing with the website medium. In this general competition, it is the print medium that lags behind, only because, it is adamant regarding its rules. It does not budge, it refuses to change itself and it greets rigidity. As a result, it has become difficult for it, to compete with the other two media.

It is a fact that the very common man, the simplest of the simple, is, even today, turning towards the print medium: that is the type-writer typing process. There are some Indians who have to depend upon, for information, absolutely on the print-medium. It is the lowest stratum of society that resorts to the ground level print-medium.

So long as, the modern miracles in the technology cannot reach the ground level- the countryside cultural environment, so long as the intellectual currents to accept the fresh and new ideas are not created among the commonest of the common, I think the old print medium has to compete with the other advanced media- only to serve the poor and developing people from the rural masses of India.

The Nature of Language Used in the Title –

Generally, the headline of a printed matter should be restricted to 8 to 10 words, to avoid the irrelevant scope of the adjectives and the descriptive terms. The print media has to take into account the multi-faceted socio-cultural, political and economic-factors, which are correct and contemporary; otherwise the title will not attract the readers.

To attract and increase the number of readers the print media should consider many things before writing a title. It is a well-known thing that the printed matter and its title are intrinsically related to each other. One cannot exactly tell whether the title gives birth to description or the description leads one to the title. Being co-related the description and the title must be congruous. And there should be an innate affiliation between them. As the readers, we cannot throw light on the archetypes of the printing process. But, we can say that some unconscious forces of mind along with the conscious forces are working while writing anything in words. So when we analyze our motives behind our writing, we can tell whether the writing description proceeds from the title or the title comes as an offshoot of the description.

Being very short in itself, barely composed in the 8 or 10 words, the title itself answers almost all the questions that may rise in the minds of the readers: where, when, why, how and who and the like. The readers suddenly understand just after reading the title- what has happened? Where did it happen? When did it happen? And who did it and Why?

Of course, the reader's imaginative sensibility or conjecture plays an important role in this sudden understanding. The reader understands the type of the news just from its title. E.g. the news-story may be a poem, may be about a novel, or about drama, or autobiography or biography or it may be a real life-story or event from socio-political life.

The title of the printed matter works at its many levels: e.g. local, regional, state-level, national-level and the international-level depending upon the area covered by the news. Many regularly and irregularly published periodicals-dailies, magazines, books,

Booklets, pamphlets and wall-papers are still serving the grass-root ground-level in India.

The language used in the title changes as per the level of the printed news-story. e.g. If one selects an attractive title- 'the Higher Educational commodity in Bazaar- Prof. Patil', one comes to know that many language skills are used in the title. The title becomes attractive and effective with the use of poetic-devices like, simile, metaphor and personification. Therefore the titles are generally rich in the poetic language. Of course, the common man with his common imaginative sensibility understands, the 'heart of the matter', without reading the whole news-story. One simply does not need the detailed reading. One can simply guess, and test his or her guessing which seems to be correct. If the level of the news-story increases- i.e. if it is of the national or the international level, the title has to be concise and objective. e.g. 'Pranab does some budget correction', 'Pilots hijack Air India Again', 'MPs want more cartoons scrapped from textbooks'.

The printed matter has to cover various topics. And the writing differs from subject to subject and also from topic to topic.

When the topic is related to money- the financial crisis, Black-money, economic recession, scams, ransoms, liquidations, banking business, inflation, sales and purchase, profit and loss are the stock subjects discussed in the news-story.

The criminal underworld-with its hijacking, shooting, burgling, murder, frauds, deception, robbery, corruption, gun-fire and bullets attracts the attention of the common readers. When the matter is about the laws-it comes up with typical words- litigation, dispute, penalty, decision, law-suit, judgment, hearing, court-sessions and regulations etc.

Many news-stories are related to the political field. For example, the two houses of the parliament, MLAs, Zilla Parishad, Municipality, or Municipal Corporation, Panchayat Samittee and Gram Panchayat. A large variety of topics including politics, political parties, financial matters, laws, sports, police and criminal world, research and various fine arts and literature are covered by the news-stories. In the field of politics, political campaigns, political parties, their scheming and intriguing, ministries, elections, canvassing,

propaganda, criticism, conferences, sermons, pamphlets and speeches are the topics which occupy the place in any printed book or booklet or periodicals.

Who is responsible for 'hiking-prices?' – A news-story published on 13th January 2011, throws light on the overall economic situation of the people. The disputes, wise or unwise, between the two political parties, e.g. the 'Congress' and the 'Nationalist Congress' give expression to their untamed opinions very often. The political parties attacking and counter attacking each other- always find a safe place for their news-stories in any periodical.

The titles of such topics are made attractive by using words like "Khade-Bol", or "Harsh-Words" or "words as weapons", "Kalagi Tura", or "Tit for Tat", or "Palatwar" or "Counter Attack", or "Point Counter Point".

Conclusion –

India is the only country in the whole world where many languages are spoken by many ethnic groups or linguistic communities and minorities. Sometimes the original community or cultural and social connotations cannot possibly be translated into the English Language- properly. In such cases, the print media men generally use the language that is clear and simple.

Thus, with its simple and direct, and sometimes, with ornamental and figurative language- that is, with the help of similes, metaphors, and personifications and symbols- and sometimes with the interrogations- and the sarcastic remarks the language used in the titles carves out some fairly good impressions on the minds of the readers. The simple language often successfully influences its common readers. So the language used in the title, as far as possible should be simple, and the style i.e. the peculiar use of the language used by the media men in the given context also helps the common readers to understand the matter that is printed.

References –

1. Sunil Saxena, Heading Writing, Sage Publication (First Edition-2006), New Delhi.
2. Nayyar Shamsi, Journalism Language and Expression, Anmol Publications Pvt. Ltd (First Edition-2005), New Delhi.
3. <http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/headlines!> (Date- 14-01-2011), Time- 2.35 p.m.
4. <http://www.megaessays.com/> (Date- 17-01-2011), Time- 3.45 p.m.
5. The Indian Express, (Date- 08-05-2012)
6. The Indian Express, (Date- 09-05-2012)
7. The Indian Express, (Date- 14-05-2012)

